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THEORY OF ELECTRONIC HYPERTEXT IN INTERNET JOURNALISM

Abstract: This article reflects the theories about hypertext and its electronic type, which is a new phenomenon in Internet journalism. Hypertext is a creative and technical phenomenon at the same time. The concept of electronic hypertext is explained as a concept that came into practice with the development of Internet media. In the article, the unique features of it were considered and the theories were summarized.

Keywords: Hypertext, internet, segment, text, hyperlink, information, hypothesis, screen

Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада интернет журналистикада янги феномен ҳисобланган гиперматн ва унинг электрон тури ҳақидаги назариялар ўз аксини топган. Гиперматн бир вақтнинг ўзида ҳам ижодий ва техник ҳодиса. Электрон гипертекст тушунчаси интернет медиасининг ривожланиши билан амалиётга кириб келган тушунча сифатида изоҳланади.

Калит сўзлар: Гиперматн, интернет, сегмент, матн, гиперҳавола, ахборот, гипотеза, экран

Аннотация: В данной статье отражены теории о гипертексте и его электронном виде, который является новым явлением в интернет-журналистике. Гипертекст – это одновременно творческий и технический феномен. Объясняется понятие электронного гипертекста как понятие, вошедшее в практику с развитием интернет-СМИ. В статье рассматриваются его особенности и обобщаются его теории.

Ключевые слова: Гипертекст, Интернет, сегмент, текст, гиперссылка, информация, гипотеза, экран.

The concept of electronic hypertext began in the 1960s. Atama was born in 1965. This was the time when the level of development of computer technologies gave the opportunity to hypothesize before the new manifestations of the written text. The most interesting concept was used by the American mathematician and philosopher T. Nelson to refer to one of the methods of writing text on the monitor screen. Such a text should consist of individual parts in a comparative manner. T. Nelson's idea, despite its laconism, led to the most significant results, i.e. it served as a theoretical basis for this written text on the Internet. According to the author of Zhoibar, "hypertext is an unstructured text, more precisely, a branched text that gives the reader the opportunity

to choose"[1]. With its help, a new text can be created, and the audience can choose different ways depending on their character and flow of opinions. It is unexpected that T. Nelson applied to the ideas "not technical in nature, but practical" in solving the technical problems of electronic text creation. That is, the name of this place is called "Xanadu", which means "magical place". At the same time, there were other uses of hypertext. However, most of them are evaluated from a technical, physical, and linguistic point of view, rather than from a technical point of view. Even so, it should be noted that today there are many attempts to model hypertext journalism and successful communication, from the linguistic point of view.

In modern journalism, the term hypertext has acquired several terminological paradigms at the same time, and its application is considered as a "communication method"[2]. The situation related to the use of the term is complex, and it also applies to the technologies supported by certain programs. L.G. According to Ovanesbekov's opinion, "from a traditional point of view, the content of hypertext consists of the fact that it is a hybrid of several traditional technologies" [3]. More specifically, it is a type of interactive interface. The idea of connecting texts in space and time was considered impossible until now. In it, intertextual hyper textuality becomes a phenomenon that occurs not in one text work, but between several texts. The same situation occurs in the Internet segment if it is in electronic hypertext.

As mentioned above, the nature of electronic hypertext is directly connected with the computer and the Internet. As its name suggests, such a hypertext provides only non-linear connections between information. That's right, its nature is intended only for information and messages in electronic form. In this regard, V. P. Rudnev notes in his "Encyclopedic Dictionary of XX Secret Culture": "Hypertext is like fate: a person is on the street in a cheerful mood, waiting for something good, suddenly some button is pressed (come on, who pressed this button and why?" (let's not give him meaningless, misleading questions) and his life changed completely. He began to live a different life, as if he had left the world. But then someone presses a button and returns him to the same place, the same street, the same thoughts. This is "Ayub's story". Hypertext content is related to such metaphorical hyperonization"[4]. That is, hypertext becomes a certain model, more like the concept of a planet. Interrelated texts are branched between spaces. "Ayub's Tale" is based on the concept of hypertext, and the main text goes to the materials of another destination, time, and returns to the same text again thanks to the links in the composition.

Within the framework of the modern scientific paradigm, the concept of electronic hypertext has been discussed in different ways by researchers based on its peculiarities:

a) as a clear text structure (Gromov, 1992, 1993; Subbotin, 1993, 1994; Hartung, Breido, 1996, Wiesel, 1999; Derrida, 2000; Kuper, 2000, Bart, 2001; Baranov, 2011; Dedova, 2003; Kalmikov, Kokhanova, 2005). Here the focus is on the textual component of the hypertext. For example, O.V. Baranov evaluates the hypertext as a new type of text, which is opposite to the plain text in Gutenberg's concept, while V.P.

Rudnev proposes the theory that hypertext is a hierarchy of texts that is a unity and plurality of texts at the same time.

b) in the characteristic of the channel method of information delivery (Conklin, 1987; Subbotin, 1993; Ovanesbekov, 1993; Ageev, 1994; Shutkin, 1995; Foltz, 1996; Wiesel, 1999; Chardin, 1999; Ryabov, 2001; Uzilevsky, 1998, 1999 and others). There, researchers see hypertext as a multi-dimensional item. It is known as the method of presenting information in the form of a network of connected nodes.

c) as a systematic constructive projection (Ageev, 2002; Nesterov, 1995; Polikaxin, Savin, 1993; Potapova, 2005). In this, the specific role is related to the structural differences in the information system and the algorithmic features of the technical implementation.

Today, there are different scientific issues related to the issue of hypertext journalism. For instance, in the article "Journalistic hypertext in the victory communications system" [5] by A. Kalmikov, the concept of "journalist hypertext" was discussed. However, the type of electronic hypertext given by the author does not fully cover the theory about it. In our opinion, hypertext is a collection of potentially infinite texts connected by a system of hyperlinks. We understand journalistic electronic hypertext as a type of hypertextual features, which is used in electronic communication for the purpose of expanding the message presented by journalists. Here, references to journalistic materials are used according to the relevant text. Links to expand the information front of the publication, opinions on the issues raised, and links to additional multimedia information are provided.

Hypertext links are widespread in Internet journalism. For this reason, many developers attribute it to the peculiarities of online media itself. Electronic hypertext is the most important feature of Internet media, it is aimed at improving the text flow with the help of hyperlinks.

We consider hypertext useful in Internet journalism from the following five points of view:

- 1) Specify the purpose of the site in the description of the site
- 2) Nature of information
- 3) As one of the technical elements of web design solutions
- 4) In terms of characteristics of the content
- 5) As a service that expands the message.

Hypertext is considered to be a factor that determines the purpose of the site. If the website is busy with multimedia content distribution, the demand for the service that links the multimedia elements to each other will obviously increase. As a result, the number of hyperlinked materials on the site increases. That is why electronic

hypertext plays the function of creating material on sites. For example, in the January 13, 2023, issue of the website www.qalampir.uz, the material "Dead body of Hollywood actor and girls who fell into the Caribbean Sea was found" was given as a link to "www.gazeta.ru", that is, the actor who died as a result of a plane crash into the sea on January 4. The news about the dead bodies of Christian Oliver and his two daughters was published on the Russian website gazeta.ru by Alina Odaeva, "Actor Christian Oliver died in an air catastrophe with two daughters." And this material is linked to the article of "Daily Mail" "Hollywood actor Christian Oliver, 51, who appeared in Speed Racer is revealed as victim of Caribbean plane crash that also killed his daughters aged 10 and 12 and pilot".

Therefore, the purpose of this site in providing this material is to deliver the world's best news to the audience. From that, hypertext is a means of combining information in space and time.

Literatures:

1. Чилингир Е.Ю. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/gipertekst-v-literature-zhurnalistike-i-piare-sotsiokulturnyy-aspekt>
2. Купер И. Р. Гипертекст как способ коммуникации // Социологический журнал. М., 2000. № 1/2. - с. 36-57.
3. Ованесбеков Л. Г. Технология построения гипертекстов. Дисс. ... канд. физмат, наук. М., 1993.
4. Руднев В. П. Энциклопедический словарь культуры XX века. Ключевые понятия и тексты. М., 2001.
5. Калмыков А. А. Гипертекст журналистики в системе массовых коммуникаций [Электронный ресурс] / А. А. Калмыков // - 2004. - Режим доступа.